

DEPORTATION OF THE PEOPLES OF THE NORTH CAUCASUS IN THE 1940S**Mamraimov S.D.***Ph.D., Associate Professor
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The deportation of the peoples of the North Caucasus to Kazakhstan during the 1940s stands as one of the most tragic episodes in the history of the Soviet Union. Under Joseph Stalin's repressive policies, ethnic groups such as the Chechens, Ingush, Balkars, and Karachays were forcibly removed from their native Caucasian lands and resettled in remote regions of Kazakhstan and Central Asia. While the Soviet government officially justified these deportations by alleging collaboration with Nazi Germany, most scholars interpret them as a component of a broader strategy of ethnic cleansing and systemic repression within the USSR.

Keywords: Soviet government, socio-demographic situation, repression, deportation, Stalinist policy, forced resettlement.

Introduction: The forced deportation of North Caucasian ethnic groups to Kazakhstan and other regions of Central Asia during the 1940s affected approximately 600,000 to 650,000 individuals. This tragic event was a direct result of Joseph Stalin's repressive policies and significantly disrupted the lives of these communities. Although the death of Stalin in 1953 opened the possibility for these exiled peoples to return to their ancestral homelands, the process of rehabilitation was protracted and fraught with obstacles. While some were able to resettle in the North Caucasus, many were denied the opportunity to fully restore their lives in their former territories.

The long-term consequences of these deportations extend beyond individual communities, influencing interethnic relations and shaping political and social processes in the post-Soviet space.

These events and their aftermath offer critical lessons that illuminate broader historical patterns:

1. **Ineffectiveness of Repression:** The Soviet policy of mass deportations and repressions proved counterproductive in the long term. Instead of resolving political or social challenges, it destabilized regional socio-economic conditions, exacerbated interethnic conflicts, and deepened public distrust in state institutions.

2. **Ongoing Rehabilitation Challenges:** The rehabilitation of displaced communities remains a pressing issue even decades later. Addressing these injustices requires robust efforts in historical acknowledgment, restitution of rights, and restoration of territories to support national reconciliation and unity.

3. **Generational Impact:** The social, economic, and psychological consequences of deportation continue to affect several generations. Many displaced peoples faced significant challenges in rebuilding their cultural identity and social structures, while the collective trauma of forced displacement remains deeply embedded in their collective memory.

4. **Contribution despite Adversity:** Despite immense hardships, the exiled peoples of the North Caucasus demonstrated remarkable resilience and adaptability. They made significant contributions to the economic, cultural, and social development of Kazakhstan, showcasing their capacity to thrive against all odds.

5. **The Importance of Historical Memory:** The deportation of these communities underscores the critical need to preserve historical memory. Learning from such events is essential to prevent similar tragedies in the future and to promote justice and reconciliation.

The deportation of the North Caucasian peoples is not just a historical tragedy but a reminder of the enduring need to address injustices, foster understanding between diverse communities, and build policies that strengthen social cohesion.

The deportation profoundly impacted ethnic groups and reshaped the social fabric of entire regions. Addressing the rehabilitation of displaced peoples and acknowledging their suffering are essential steps toward fostering interethnic harmony and establishing a fair and just society.

Studying these events is crucial to preventing the recurrence of similar tragedies. Recognizing historical errors and fostering cultural and historical dialogue among peoples are vital components for promoting peace and stability in modern Kazakhstan and the broader post-Soviet space.

Deportation of peoples was a hallmark of Stalinist repression in the USSR. Its defining characteristics included extrajudicial decisions, forced relocations, and the socially disruptive transfer of significant portions of the population to remote, unfamiliar regions [1, p.5].

As noted by Pavel Polyansky, eleven ethnic groups were entirely deported in the USSR, including Koreans, Germans, Finns, nomads, Kalmyks, Chechens, Ossetians, Ingush, Balkars, Crimean Tatars, and Meskhetian Turks. Among these, seven groups—Germans, nomads, Kalmyks, Ingush, Chechens, Balkars, and Crimean Tatars—were stripped of their national autonomy [2, p.46].

While earlier deportations, such as those from the Far East before World War II, were officially described by Soviet authorities as "voluntary resettlements," later deportations received widespread criticism. In February 2004, the European Parliament officially recognized these actions as genocide and crimes against humanity [3].

In the 2010s, some historians challenged the term "deportation" in reference to the forced resettlement of USSR residents to its peripheries. Scholars such as Ni-

kolai Bugai advocated for the term "forced resettlement" instead, arguing it better reflects the nature of these actions [4, p.118]. Similarly, participants of the 2017 international symposium 1937: Russian-Speaking Koreans – Past, Present, and Future, held in Vladivostok, adopted a resolution emphasizing that "deportation" should not be used to describe forced resettlements within the USSR [5].

The deportation of peoples was a deliberate aspect of the USSR's national policy, driven by several strategic objectives:

1) Instilling fear as a tool of governance: Deportations were intended to create a climate of fear that enabled centralized control and suppression of dissent;

2) Fragmenting internal unity and promoting ethnic assimilation: By forcibly displacing populations, the Soviet regime sought to weaken the cultural and social cohesion of ethnic groups, thereby facilitating their assimilation into a homogenized Soviet identity;

3) Shifting blame for regime failures: The policy aimed to deflect responsibility for the military, political, and economic missteps of the Soviet leadership onto the deported peoples, portraying them as scapegoats for systemic issues;

4) Increasing population in underdeveloped regions: Deportations were used to bolster the population in sparsely inhabited areas such as Siberia, Kazakhstan, and Central Asia, aligning with the Soviet agenda of regional development;

5) Providing labor resources to underdeveloped regions: The displaced peoples were also seen as a means to supply labor to economically backward regions, contributing to the development of these areas within the Soviet Union [6].

Materials and methods: This study employs a systematic approach to collecting and analyzing research materials, including textbooks, scientific works, and archival data. The primary objective of the research is to uncover previously overlooked aspects of history and provide detailed insights into the challenging period experienced by the deported peoples. The methodology integrates various research techniques to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the topic. Specific historical methods were employed to examine events within their unique context, while comparative historical methods allowed for the identification of patterns and differences across similar events. Analytical methods were utilized to interpret data and draw meaningful conclusions, and collective and generalizing methods helped synthesize findings into coherent narratives. By leveraging these diverse approaches, the study aims to present a nuanced account of this complex historical period, grounded in reliable and specific data sources.

Discussion of the results: As in many other countries, political repression in Kazakhstan had serious consequences for society and individuals. During the Soviet era (especially in the 1930s and 1950s), mass political repression in Kazakhstan affected various groups of the population, including the intelligentsia, peasantry, ethnic minorities, and religious groups.

- The peculiarities of political repression in Kazakhstan include:

- Many peoples were forced to leave their historical homeland and move to other regions of the Soviet Union. For example, the deportation of Germans, Koreans, Chechens, and other nationalities.

- Many intellectuals, scientists, writers, historians, and other public figures became victims of political persecution for their beliefs or criticism of the policies of the Soviet government.

- Churches and religious associations were also persecuted. Religious leaders were arrested, churches were closed, and believers were discriminated against.

- The forced collectivization of agriculture in the 1930s led to a famine that took the lives of millions of Kazakhs.

- The Turkestan region, like many other regions, has a rich and complex history of peoples and cultures. For many centuries, this region was an object of migration and conquest by various ethnic groups.

1943-1944: The peoples of the North Caucasus – Kalmyks, Ingush, Chechens, nomads, Balkars, Crimean Tatars, Nogais, Meskhetian Turks, Greeks, Bulgarians, Crimean Gypsies, Kurds – were forcibly resettled mainly on charges of collaborating with the enemy, banditry, and armed struggle against the Soviet government. In fact, it was not possible to find a single document confirming anti-Soviet activities and charges of treason during the war.

During the Great Patriotic War, 16,944 families and 59,398 people settled in the Turkestan region. Of these:

- Karachaylar – 4,705 families, 17,649 people
- Chechen-Ingushetia – 4,270 families, 14,730 people
- Kabardino-Balkarians – 610 families, 1,964 people
- Georgians – 2,385 families, 9,558 people
- Crimeans – 63 families, 163 people
- Germans – 4,904 families, 15,317 people
- Kalmaks – 7 families, 17 people

The overwhelming majority of able-bodied special emigrants joined collective farms, worked as collective farmers and laborers on state farms, and their children studied in primary and secondary schools. For example, 556 immigrant families live in Shymkent, including 345 Chechens, 100 nomads, and 12 Kurds, a total of 1,711 people. 747 people worked in production, most of them were engaged in their profession: 1 person was an agronomist, 6 people were veterinarians, 10 people were accountants, 8 people were field and zoo-technicians, 69 people worked as tractor drivers and combine operators. 75 tractor drivers, 14 combine operators, 13 junior veterinary paramedics, livestock technicians, and veterinary nurses were trained at special courses.

In the first years, only 60% of able-bodied special settlers participated in collective and state farm production; there were cases of dishonesty, absenteeism, refusal to work, theft, etc. However, over time, the majority of able-bodied people worked in production, and among them, cases of violation of labor discipline and misconduct became rare. Most of them were active in work and showed good productivity.

The settlers were provided with livestock and housing. Livestock for personal use was provided to 4,966 families; small livestock was given to 5,562 families. 8,602 families were provided with private houses, 12,261 families lived in houses of collective farms, state farms, and other enterprises, and 1,948 families lived in the homes of individuals.

In 1948, according to the approved plan of the Union government, 2,846 dwellings were built for collective farmers, most of which were transferred to special settlers. During this period, special settlers received 21,001.2 centners of cattle, 281.6 centners of food, 320,500 soms in cash benefits, 274 centners of wool,

610 pieces of skins, 6,925 centners of fur, and 6,925 thousand sheep.

The resolution of the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR, adopted in May 1944, stipulated that each family of special settlers should receive one head of cattle with an average live weight of 200 kg, and in the absence of cattle, sheep and small livestock. Small animals should be given at the rate of 200 kg of live weight per head of cattle. However, the special settler was given a cow or a sheep and was immediately taxed in kind and money. Often, people sold this cow to pay the taxes. In 1945, special settlers were exempted from taxes.

Information on employment of migrants

№	District	Number of families	Kolkhoz Family	Family State Farm	Family Production Capacity	Family Institutions and Organizations
1	Arys	1021	648	300	10	63
2	Bostandyk	538	44	-	414	80
3	Jualy	724	477	53	26	168
4	Ilyich	1470	467	770	102	129
5	Kirov	385	126	259	-	-
6	Karatas	470	320	150	-	-
7	Kyzylkum	464	66	345	-	53
8	Keles	523	437	-	20	16
9	Georgiev	1403	930	-	464	9
10	Pakhta-Aral	952	739	110	73	25
11	Sairam	1196	1140	46	10	-
12	Sary-Agash	1022	464	427	47	84
13	Tulkibas	1046	431	65	393	157
14	Turkistan	843	310	90	440	3
15	Shayan	535	514	-	6	15
16	Shauldir	87	61	21	5	-
	Total	12899	7251	2810	2036	802

1,351 representatives of the immigrant Chechen-Ingush nationality worked in the coal industry, and 898 people worked in non-ferrous metallurgy. Among the resettled special settlers, 17,512 people were able to work, of which 18,072 were working. This figure indicates that teenagers were also involved in socially useful work.

All special settlers were placed in collective farms across 7,252 households, and all were accepted as members of collective farms in accordance with the charter of the agricultural artel. They received individual allotments on an equal basis with all collective farmers. Additionally, those who settled in production farms from 4,016 households received individual plots of land for planting gardens. In 1946, the families of special settlers planted vegetable gardens as an additional source of food. As of July 1, 1946, special settlers in the Turkestan region were housed in the following manner:

1. In new buildings - 782 families.
2. In purchased houses - 1,075 families.
3. In houses of economic institutions - 6,538 families.
4. In houses handed over for permanent use - 6,538 families.
5. Together with local residents - 732 families. Total: 12,899 families.

The implementation of the housing construction plan provided the region with building materials, including 359 cubic meters of wood materials and 2,450 units of window glass. This volume of materials was sufficient for the construction of only 100 houses, but 782 houses were built due to the use of local building materials. Since the region had no wood, the purchase of ready-made materials was organized. In 1944, 1,075 houses were built, and in 1945, 843 houses were purchased, 396 new houses were built, and 2,589 houses were repaired.

From 1946, special settlers began to take their work seriously, understanding that they would not return to the Caucasus. For example, foreman Kaimov D., and workers Dokayev T., Lakayev, and Kaimov Zakerya at the Darbaza station of the Soyuzformit quarry in the Saryagash district exceeded production standards by 150-250 percent.

In the Kaplanbek district, the canal was heavily blocked, and district leaders organized a Sunday action. A team of 23 special settlers participated in cleaning the canal and increased productivity to 300%. They were awarded for their efforts. In the Zhualynsky district, a tractor brigade led by Mamadov from the Burno-Oktjabrskaya MTS received a bonus of one sheep per brigade member for exceeding the plan during the spring sowing.

The Karashaylar brigade, a special settler group from the Stalin branch of the Pakhtaaraal state farm in the Ilyichsky district, brought the production index to 170 percent, received a bonus, and won the state farm's variable Red Banner for the second consecutive year. At the Keltemashatugol mine, miner-special settler Shakh-tiyev consistently exceeded the coal production quota month after month and received an average income of 4,000-4,500 soms.

In preparation for the deportation, a range of measures aimed at the economic regulation of settled families was considered. However, the implementation of these measures faced challenges due to objective and subjective reasons. The difficult situation was exacerbated by a lack of material and economic resources, harsh climatic conditions, and occasional neglect by local authorities.

As a result, the morbidity and mortality of special settlers led to significant casualties. For example, in 1944, 32,502 people died in Kazakhstan, and in 1945, 32,111 people. The highest mortality occurred in the second half of 1944 and the first half of 1945, coinciding with the fall, winter, and spring of the first year of acclimatization. This period also coincided with food shortages and the lack of appropriate clothing and footwear" [10].

During this period, 857 people died in the Tulkibas district of the Turkestan region, or 23 percent of those who migrated to the region. In the Turkestan region, 35 people died of weakness in July 1944. From March to September 1, 1944, 376 people died from various diseases in the Kuyik district, including 150 children. From March to September 1944, 340 people died at the Keltemashtuugol mine.

In May 1944, 13 people died of typhus in the Bostaniksky district, and 4 people died of beatings on suspicion of theft. From March 1944 to June 1945, 1,321 people died in the Zhualisky district, which amounted to 32 percent of the total number of emigrants to the district. During this period, 1,263 people died in the Lengensky district, or 22.5% of the total number of settlers. The mortality rate in the Turkestan region was 25.6% of the total number of special settlers [11].

On January 17, 1956, the Decree of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet was issued lifting restrictions on the Poles expelled in 1936; on March 17, 1956, it was lifted for Kalmyks; on March 27, for Greeks, Bulgarians, and Armenians; on April 18, 1956, for Crimean Tatars, Balkars, Meskhetian Turks, Kurds, and Hemshils; and on July 16, 1956, legal restrictions were lifted from Chechens, Ingush, and nomads, who had not had the right to return to their homeland.

In 1957-1958, the national autonomies of Kalmyks, Chechens, Ingush, Khmers, and Balkars were restored, and these peoples were allowed to return to their historical territories. The return of the oppressed peoples was not without difficulties and led both then and later to national conflicts. However, a significant number of persecuted peoples-Volga Germans, Crimean Tatars, Meskhetian Turks, Greeks, and Koreans-did not regain the right to return to their historical homeland.

On August 29, 1964, the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR, by Decree No. 2820-VI, cancelled the mass condemnation of the German people. Since the mid-1960s, the process of rehabilitation of the "punished peoples" has been completed [12].

One of the first steps towards restoring historical justice for persecuted peoples was the adoption of the Declaration of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR on November 14, 1989, "On the recognition of the acts of persecution of peoples subjected to forced displacement as illegal and criminal and ensuring their rights." According to it, all oppressed peoples, slander against them, genocide, forced displacement, destruction of national-state structures, the policy of establishing a regime of terror and violence in special places, and repressive actions at the state level were recognized as illegal and criminal.

On April 26, 1991, the Law of the RSFSR No. 1107-I "On the Protection of Repressed Peoples" was adopted, in which the deportation of peoples was recognized as "a policy of slander and genocide." In addition, the law recognized the right of oppressed peoples to restore the territorial integrity that existed before the unconstitutional policy of violent redrawing of borders, to restore the national-state structures that existed before their destruction, and to compensate the accused state for damages caused by violations of the law [13].

As for the scientific and methodological issues regarding the full legal and political rehabilitation of victims of persecution, we believe they include the following:

- Many archival materials on persecution remain closed or inaccessible to researchers and descendants of victims.

- Due to the political situation and the influence of various interests, objective assessment of the scale and consequences of repression remains problematic.

- To honor the past and restore the honor and dignity of victims and their families, it is crucial to conduct research on the victims of repression and compile memorial books.

- It is necessary to develop and adopt appropriate laws and measures aimed at fully rehabilitating victims of political persecution and their family members, including the payment of compensation and restoration of violated rights.

These issues require great attention from the state, public organizations, and the scientific community to ensure justice and remembrance of the victims of political repression in Kazakhstan. The deportation of peoples to Kazakhstan had profound social, economic, and cultural consequences in the history of the country. Here are some key issues related to this deportation:

- Deportations, particularly under Soviet rule, were often accompanied by humanitarian tragedies. Many people died or found themselves in difficult living conditions due to a lack of necessary resources and assistance.

- Family ties were severed as a result of the deportations, with family members being separated and forced to remain in different regions.

- Many ethnic groups exiled to Kazakhstan had their own languages, traditions, and cultures. The deportations led to the loss or significant distortion of this cultural heritage.

- The expelled peoples often faced difficulties in providing for themselves and their families in the new environment. Economic integration was hindered by a lack of resources and infrastructure.

- The deportations caused deep psychological trauma to the displaced persons and their descendants. The loss of their place of origin, the breakdown of family structures, and the drastic changes in living conditions created lasting emotional scars that could be passed down through generations.

- Many deportees and their descendants feel the need for formal rehabilitation and compensation for the harm and suffering caused by these injustices.

These issues highlight the need for thorough research and recognition of the historical legacy of deportations in Kazakhstan. Moreover, measures must be implemented to assist the victims and preserve their cultural heritage

Conclusion: The history of the deportations is a crucial chapter that has shaped Kazakhstan's multicultural society and identity. The lessons learned from this painful period emphasize the importance of preserving peace and harmony for both present and future generations.

Despite enduring harsh conditions and discrimination, the exiled peoples made significant contributions to the country's culture, economy, and social fabric. Today, Kazakhstan takes pride in its ethnic diversity and its tradition of tolerance.

The memory of the exiles continues to resonate in the national consciousness and history of the country. This period serves as a reminder of past injustices, while also highlighting the potential for interethnic harmony in a multiethnic state.

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